

Popular Article

Clinical Management of Canine Pyometra: A Mini Review

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Abstract

Canine pyometra is an endometrial pathology that causes the uterus to become clogged with a purulent, semisolid substance. A sequence of cystic endometrial hyperplasia (CEH), which is brought on by hormonal imbalance. Because the afflicted animal may become very dehydrated, septicemic, fall into shock, die from toxæmia alone, or be coupled with peritonitis from uterine rupture, prompt diagnosis and treatment of canine pyometra are crucial.

Keywords: Canine Pyometra, Progesterone, Diagnosis, Pathogenesis, Treatment.

Introduction

Canine pyometra is a frequent reproductive syndrome that affects sexually mature, intact female dogs throughout the met/diestrous stage and manifests as a variety of systemic and reproductive-specific clinical and pathological symptoms (Fransson, 2003). Pyometra or chronic purulent endometritis as an accumulation of pus in the uterus. It is a prevalent metestrous disease with a median age of 10 years and primarily affects bitches between the ages of 9 months and 18 years (Jitpean et al., 2012). The illness typically strikes after oestrus and typically during the luteal phase (Blendinger, 1997). Several terms, such as chronic endometritis, chronic purulent metritis or cystic endometrial hyperplasia pyometra complex (CEHPC), have been used in the literature to describe the condition (Fakuda, 2001).

Based on the condition of the cervix, canine Pyometra can be classified as either open-cervix or closed-cervix; however, the closed form is a more serious condition that requires surgical intervention to prevent concurrent infection and mortality (Smith, 2006).

It is a consequence of cystic endometrial hyperplasia and accumulation of exudate in the uterus as the most severe end stage (Dow, 1957). Dow described four stages of canine pyometra: Stage I, uncomplicated cystic endometrial hyperplasia; Stage II, cystic endometrial hyperplasia with plasma cell infiltrate; Stage III, cystic endometrial hyperplasia with acute endometritis; Stage IV, cystic endometrial hyperplasia with chronic endometritis.

Nulliparous bitches have a moderately higher risk of developing pyometra than primiparous and multiparous animals (Niskanen and Thrusfield, 1998).

Hagman (2004) reported 25% that of the female dog population developed pyometra by 10 years of age which is a very high incidence compared to other uterine problems.

Etiology

- Several studies suggested that progesterone and estrogen, the two reproductive hormones, play a major role in predisposing to pyometra, with the former being the most important one. The well-established effects of progesterone on endometrial gland secretions and myometrial contraction, which encourage bacterial growth and colonization well known (Cox, 1970).
- Estrogen plays a secondary role by improving progesterone's endometrial responsiveness. The most prevalent occurrence of *E. coli* and endotoxins can be used to determine the etiology of bacterial origin (Hageman, 2004; Bondade et al., 2010) Numerous other pathogenic bacteria, such as *Klebsiella Spp.*, *Streptococci*, *Staphylococci*, anaerobic bacteria, and *Pseudomonads*, are also identified as the causative agent (Dhaliwal et al., 1998). The virulence factors of *E. coli*, such as K antigen and cytotoxin necrotizing factor, are associated with pathological conditions.
- Parity and age are significant risk factors in the development of pyometra (Niskanen and Thrusfield 1998).
- Several researchers have said that progesterone and the host's sensitivity to pathogenic germs appear to be key factors in the development of disease (Krekeler et al., 2012a; 2012b).

Prevalence, background, and clinical observations

Kumar and Saxena (2018) reported that canine pyometra is commonly presented in mature bitches ranging from 4 to 16 years, but most common at the age of 7.5 years with regular and repeated estrous cycle. The occurrence was reported as 19% in bitches below 10 years of age and 20% in older female dogs. Breed susceptibility is also observed in this condition with high risk include Rottweiler, Saint Bernard, Chow chow, Golden Retriever, Miniature Schnauzer, Irish Terrier, Airedale Terrier, Cavalier King Charles Spaniel, Rough Collie, and Bernese Mountain dog. Moreover, a few breeds possess low risk like German shepherd, Daschunds and Swedish hounds. Breed susceptibility strongly indicates the contribution of genotype towards increase or decrease risk of disease.

Pathogenesis

Blood progesterone levels rise during the luteal phase of the estrous cycle, which in turn causes an increase in endometrial gland secretions, endometrial growth, decreased myometrial contraction, and cervix closure (Hardie, 1995) all of which favour the development of illness. Bacterial factors and the expression of their receptors may promote bacterial adhesion to endometrium (Gabriel et al., 2016).

According to Wijewardana et al. (2015), progesterone has a deleterious effect on the development of antigen-presenting dendritic cells, which may lower cell-mediated immunity (CMI).

Gultiken et al. (2016) showed elevated expression of 3-hydroxy steroid dehydrogenase on endometrial tissue in pigs with pyometra, further indicating the role of local progesterone production in the development of the disease, even when it is within normal limits. Due to lowered local immunity and decreased CMI brought on by progesterone dominance in the luteal phase (Sugiura et al., 2004), infections can develop and colonize the uterus more quickly.

Clinical Signs and Diagnosis

Haematological and biochemical parameters

Shah *et al.*, (2017) studied the hematological parameters in 6 clinical cases of pyometra-affected bitches with different breeds and reported that

Parameter	Units	Patient data		Reference range*
		Mean \pm SE	Observation range	
Hb	g/dl	5.62 \pm 0.32	2.0 – 8.2	12 - 18
RBC	$\times 10^6/\mu\text{l}$	3.24 \pm 0.59	1.8 – 4.9	5.5 – 8.8
PCV	%	18.55 \pm 1.18	8 - 25	37 - 55
MCV	Fl	60.88 \pm 6.71	44.4 - 80	60 - 77
MCH	Pg	20.55 \pm 1.85	11.1 – 21.6	19.5 - 24.5
MCHC	%	33.3 \pm 3.37	21 – 38.4	32 - 36
WBC	$\times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$	104.8 \pm 4.0	81.2 – 131.2	6 - 17
Neutrophils	%	94.25 \pm 0.73	92 - 96	60-70
Lymphocytes	%	5.25 \pm 0.41	4 - 6	30-40
Platelets	$\times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$	182.5 \pm 17.01	100 - 250	200 - 500
Reticulocytes	%	1.29 \pm 0.64	1.5 – 4.5	0.0 – 1.5
BUN	mg/dl	63.6 \pm 7.07	30.4 – 110.4	7 – 32
Creatinine	mg/dl	2.96 \pm 0.6	1.9 – 4.0	0.5 – 1.4
Albumin	g/dl	2.93 \pm 0.03	2.9 – 3.0	3.2 – 4.2
Total protein	g/dl	9.53 \pm 0.78	8 – 10.6	5.3 – 7.6
ALP	IU/L	154.66 \pm 7.72	129 - 180	0 – 90
ALT	IU/L	43.66 \pm 4.68	33 - 63	10 – 94
AST	IU/L	55.66 \pm 1.71	51 - 63	10 - 62

Pathology

Gross Lesion

Gupta *et al.*, (2015) studied the gross changes in the uterus of bitches with pyometra. Grossly, blood mixed reddish-brown to greyish-white contents with watery to thick creamy consistency was observed in the lumen of uterus. The endometrium was smooth in most cases and thickened in few cases. Uterus in pyometra was dilated with purulent to sanguino-purulent materials.

Histopathology

Schlafer and Gifford (2008) reported that the most common histopathological finding in pyometra is the progression of events starting with the development of endometrial hyperplasia, with or without cyst formation. Endometrial hyperplasia is associated with uterine bacterial infection in bitches. This stimulates a local inflammatory reaction and in turn the hyperplastic endometrium causes secretions to accumulate, followed by the establishment of a bacterial infection. This results in the accumulation of exudate in the uterine lumen leading to pyometra. Small aggregates of cystic endometrial glands sometimes stimulate deposition of interstitial fibrous connective tissue that can expand and protrude to form endometrial polyps. Bitches and queens may have only one or several endometrial polyps, which are frequently small and of little consequence. Occasionally larger polyps develop that can compromise the uterine lumen.

Radiographical examination and Ultrasonography

Baithalu *et al.*, (2010) stated that the diagnosis of pyometra is best made with the help of radiology used as an aid in diagnosis of pyometra in the bitch. In pyometra radiographically, a fluid dome, tubular structure should be seen in the ventral and caudal abdomen, displacing loops of intestine dorsally and cranially. The pyometra may be difficult to palpate uterine enlargement, especially in case of open cervix pyometra and in case of large and obese bitch. In case of closed cervix pyometra the degree of uterine distension is greater and may be associated with visible enlargement.

Rautela and Katiyar (2019) reported that ultrasonography reveals an enlarged uterus with convoluted, tubular horns containing anechoic or hypoechoic fluid with thickened endometrium. The luminal contents are usually homogenous and echo-dense due to pus particles. The presence of cystic structures with thickened endometrium is diagnostic for CEH with or without pyometra. Ultrasonography is the best diagnostic method that has been used for diagnosis of pyometra.

Figure 1: Pus Filled Uterine Horn on Caesarean Section

Figure 2: Distention of the uterus with an anechoic to hyperechoic fluid

Radiographic Examples of Pyometra

Patient A (Ventral View)

Patient B (Ventral View)

Patient A (Lateral View)

Patient B (Lateral View)

Treatment

Surgical Approach

Kumar and Saxena (2018) stated that spaying remains the choice of treatment for majority of obstetrician, however recently Laparoscopic Assisted Ovariectomy (LAOVH) is advocated for

treatment of select cases of canine pyometra, which is proved to be efficacious over conventional open method with careful case selection in order to improve success rate.

Medical Approach

The primary goals of medical treatment are the systemic and intrauterine administration of drugs. Prostaglandin (PGF_{2α}) given subcutaneously at a dose rate of 150–200 g/kg/day for more than 10 days produced 100% of the desired effects (Myhre, 2016), which may be because PGF 2α promotes luteolysis, which results in progesterone block (Renton et al., 1993). Another treatment using cloprostenol (@ 1 Pg/kg once daily) and cabergoline (@ 5 Pg/kg PO once daily) for seven days was well received.

However, progesterone blockers like mifepristone (Hoffman and Schuler, 2000) or aglepristone (Wehrend and Traschbostedt, 2003; Arnold et al., 2006) have recently proven to be a more effective treatment option.

Additionally, Contri et al. (2015) had success with a regimen that paired aglepristone with a brief (6 days) antibiotic cover. A third-generation GnRH antagonist, acyline, at 330 μg/kg orally (single dosage), combined with amoxicillin-clavulanate at 12.5 mg/kg twice a day, orally for seven days, has shown encouraging results in the treatment of pyometra (Batista et al., 2016).

Conclusion

Since canine pyometra is one of the bacterial infections that could lead to systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS), it is advised that any buck that won't be used for breeding in the future be spayed before the age of six to prevent the development of pyometra. Due to the extremely complicated nature of the disease, one of the many causes of this problem can be attributed to the absence of comprehensive and accurate information regarding the etio-pathology of canine pyometra. Finding a proven medical procedure with a high rate of recovery that may be utilised as an alternative to a demanding, expensive, and time-consuming surgical procedure is urgently needed today.

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